

DREKKANA (D3) IMPORTANCE IN MEDICAL ASTROLOGY

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Abstract:

Divisional Charts are the best source to get accurate results in Astrology. Shodasa Vargu are well proposed in Brihat parasara Hora sastra out of which Drekkana (D3) chart gives accurate body part that gets effected by the malefic planet placed in natal chart.

Key Words: Shodasa Vargu, Drekkana, malefic planet position

Objective:

To write and explain about Drekkana (Decanate) and its importance in finding ill health route cause in Medical Astrology.

Introduction:

भवनादिपैः समस्तं जाटकविहितं विचिन्तरोन्मतिमान्
एभिर्विना न शक्यं पदमपि गन्तु महाशास्त्रे

The effect of a horoscope should be predicted accounting to the strength in divisions of houses without which one cannot take even one step in Astrology

---Saravali

- Divisional charts are presented in the format of horoscope. They are derived on nirayana system with Lahiri or Chaitraksha Ayanamsha. Manthreswar in Phal Deepika have followed the Dasavarga classification but with a variation. The benefic positions are Exaltation, Own sign and Friendly sign.

- In Rasi Chakra we know the macro analyzation of a planet, where as in Divisional Chart we known to the micro analysis of a planet in the natal chart of the native.

The micro level analysis is eventually explained by Maharshi Parashara to Mythreya written in Brihat Parashara Hora sastra explained the Shodasha (16 divisions) varga charkras.

They are Rasi (1), Hora (2), Drekkana (3), Navamsha (9), Dwadasamsa (12), Trimsamsa (30) are called Shadvargas (6 vargas). Added to them Saptamsa (7) are called Saptavargas (7 Vargas), adding Dasamsa (10), Shodasamsa(16), Shatyamsa (60) are called Dasavargiya (10 vargas), adding to this Charturdhamsa (4), Vimshamsa (20), Chaturvinshamsa or Siddamsa (24), Saptavimsamsa (27), Khavedamsa or Chatvarimsha (40), Akshavedamsa (45) are called Shodasha Vargus.

- Drekkana: For the 12 rasis in the natal chart 36 drekkanas are divided with each having 10 degrees (10⁰) of preference. They govern 36parts of the human body. First 10⁰ of the each rasi in chart are head parts, second 10⁰ of each rasi as middle division parts of human body, third one is of Third division of 12 parts of the lower body of human.

House	1 st Drekkana 0 ⁰ to 10 ⁰	2 nd Drekkana 11 ⁰ to 20 ⁰	3 rd Drekkana 21 ⁰ to 30 ⁰
1	Head	Neck	Pelvis
2	Right Eye	Right Shoulder	Generating Organ
3	Right Ear	Right Arm	Right testicle
4	Right Nostril	Rightside of the body	Right thigh
5	Right Cheek	Right ventricle & auricle of heart	Right knee
6	Right Jaw	Right Lung & mamma	Right calf
7	Mouth	Naval	Legs
8	Left Jaw	Left Lung & mamma	Left calf
9	Left Cheek	Left ventricle & auricle of heart	Left knee
10	Left Nostril	Left side of the trunk	Left thigh
11	Left Ear	Left arm	Left testicle
12	Left Eye	Left shoulder	Anus

- Diseases may occur in the body organ inculcated by the Decanate when maefic planets occupy such Decanates. Out of 36 Drekkanas when some happen to be Lagna may cause diseases, death, death of poison, fire, death by hanging and other misfortunes. They are
 - Visha Drekkana (Drekkana of Poison)
 - Aayudha Drekkana (Drekkana of Weapon)
 - Kroora Drekkana (Drekkana of Cruelty)

- Mriga Drekkana (Drekkana of Animal)
- Agni Drekkana (Drekkana of Fire)
- Chatushpada Drekkana (Drekkana of four legged Animal)
- Pakshi Drekkana (Drekkana of bird)
- Sarpa Drekkana (Drekkana of snake or sarpanth)
- Kola mukha Drekkana
- Paasa Drekkana (Drekkana of rope)
- Nigada Drekkana
- 22nd Drekkana

Out of which Visha, Sarpa, Aayudha, Kroora, Agni, Chatushpada, Nigada, Paasa and 22nd drekkana would bring death or death like experiences to the native their dasa or antardasa periods.

per Brihat Parasara Hora Sastra each rasi having three drekkana (D3) will have catageristions with different natures. All 36 Drekkanas which will result in the following method.

Sign	D3	Sex	Category	Nature
Mesha	1	Male	Aayudh, Chatushpad	Kroor
	2	Female	Chatushpad	Soumya
	3	Male	Aayudh	Mixed
Vrushabha	1	Female	Chatushpad	Mixed
	2	Male	Sarpa, Chatushpad	Soumya
	3	Male	Chatushpad	Watery
Midhuna	1	Female	Chatushpad	Soumya
	2	Male	Aayudh / Pakshi	Mixed
	3	Male	Aayudh	Watery
Karkataka	1	Male	Chatushpad, Varaha	Watery
	2	Female	Sarpa	Kroor
	3	Male	Sarpa	Mixed
Simha	1	Male	Aayudh, Chatushpad, Pakshi	Kroor
	2	Male	Aayudh	Mixed
	3	Male	Aayudh, Chatushpad	Kroor
Kanya	1	Female	Pakshi	Soumya
	2	Male	Pakshi	Watery
	3	Male	Pakshi	Soumya
Tula	1	Male	Pakshi	Soumya
	2	Male	Pakshi	Mixed
	3	Male	Chatushpad	Kroor
Vrischika	1	Female	Sarpa	Kroor
	2	Female	Sarpa, Pakshi	Kroor
	3	Male	Chatushpad	Kroor
Dhanassu	1	Male	Pakshi	Mixed
	2	Female	Ratna Bhandar	Soumya
	3	Male	Aayudh	Soumya
Makara	1	Male	Chatushpad, Pakshi, Nigada	Kroor
	2	Female	Chatushpad	Soumya
	3	Male	Chatushpad	Mixed
Kumbha	1	Male	Aayudh	Kroor
	2	Female	Aayudh	Soumya
	3	Male	Aayudh	Soumya
Meena	1	Male	Aayudh	Watery
	2	Female	Aayudh	Watery
	3	Male	Sarpa	Kroor

Twenty Second (22nd) Drekkana is also called as Khara Drekkana and its lord is called Kharesh. It has important significance in horoscope. Kharesh gives malefic results. Khara means harsh, rough, donkey, hurtful, sharp, sharp edged, cruel etc.,. 22nd Drekkana will be in the 8th house of natal chart. Lord of 8th house is the lord of 22nd drekkana. Drekkana is to be calculated with degrees from Lagna of chart. As it is calculated from Lagna it evaluate and shows result of harm to physical nature. If calculated from Moon in natal chart it indicates mental agony of the native.

When malefic planets occupy a particular Drekkana, they cause Wounds or Ulsers there. When benefic occupy, only a spot or a mark or a mole on skin results.

Varahamihira in Bruhat Jataka states “ When a planet capable of causing wound or Ulser or mark is in its own house or in association of Saturn, such wound or ulser or mark present since birth, else it results later on.

समनुपतिता यस्मिन्भागे त्रयः स बुधाग्रहा
 भवति नियामान्तस्याव्यपितः शुभे स्वभूषुवा ।
 व्रणकृद् शुभः षष्टे देहे तनोर्भ समाश्रिते
 तिलकम शकृ धृष्टः सौम्यैर्युतश्च सलक्ष्मवान् ।

Any body part is represented by Four planets including any three planets and Budha, even if they are benefic or malefic out of which planet is having more strength may surely give wounds or illness to the body part it represent. The malefic planet representing the Sixth house from Lagna will give wounds or illness to the part it represent human body of the native. If the malefic planet placed rasi is fixed rasi and that planet is in own rasi and own navamsa it can be considered the illness or the wound in the place represented by the planet of human body will be there at the time of birth, if in movable sign or any other navamsa then the dasa period of planet such illness or wound will happen. If malefic in sixth house is aspecting by the benefic planet then there will be only a black mole or a white mole may seen at respective body part.

There told some other Drekkana methods after Varahamihira are namely Garga Drekkana, Varanasi Drekkana, Somnath Drekkana, Cyclical of Parivrittitraya Drekkana and Tajik Drekkana.

Example:

Male, Born on 2nd Oct.,1967 Time: 4:48AM., in Kakinada,

(Sa)	Ra		
	Natal (Rasi)Chart D1		Lg Mo Ju Ve
	Ma	Ke Me	Su

	Lg Ra		
	Drekkana Chart D3		Ju Ve
Su		Ke Me	Su

Lagna – 28° 39’ Sun – 14° 41’ Moon – 18° 29’ Mars – 21° 27’
 Mercury – 8° 59’ Jupiter – 3° 30’ Venus- 6° 41’ Saturn – 15° 41’
 Rahu – 5° 25’ Ketu – 5° 25’

- In Drekkana (D3) chart Lagna star lord is Venus and Rahu is in lagna. So, in the Dasa Period of Venus and Rahu health issue may arise to the native’s body.
- In Drekkana (D3) chart Lagna star lord is Venus. So, problem relating to Venus body part may arise.
- In Drekkana (D3) chart Rahu is in Lagna creates problem. He is in Ketu star and Mars is in Saptama Bhava. So, problem pertaining to Saptama bhava (Tula rasi) will arise.
- In Drekkana (D3) chart Lagna kshetradhpathi Mars isain Debilitation in Moons kshetra (Rasi) which is a watery sign.
- In Drekkana (D3) Mars is in debilitation and associated with Saturn who creates pain.
- In Drekkana (D3) 6th house lord Mercury which is a watery sign is in 7th house aspecting lagna.
- In Drekkana (D3) Mars who is lagnadhpathi is a Yogakaraka in Rasi (D1) char. So, he is not taken to resulting operation. As he is in watery sing so the problem resolved liquid related medicine.

Reason for Hospitalisation as per Gochara:

- In Rahu who is in lagna of Drekkana (D3) chart, in his Mahardasa of the native and Lagna starlord Antardasa the problem is raised and detected.
- Illness occurred to the native on 6th Nov.2014 at 6.00pm. in Hyderabad

Ke	Lg Mo		
	D1		Ju

	6/11/2014 6 :00 PM Hyderabad		
Ma	Sa	Me Ve Su	Ra

- 12th Lord of the Rasi Chart (D1) of Native is Moon, who is in Lagna at the time of hospitalization.
- Three Malefics on the time of hospitalization are in 6th, 7th, 8th bhavas of the Gochara Rasi chakra resulting Stones in the bladder of the Native.

Conclusion:

Drekkana Chakra plays a vital role in finding the occurrence of the illness and to which part of body it effects. A Thorough further study is needed for the more accuracy in findings of time and date of illness to the natives.

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